

The Manipulation of Religion by Political Gladiators in Nigeria

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Abstract

Religion has always been manipulated for political ends particularly in Nigeria starting from campaign, rally, and policy formulation and voting behaviour. Politicians seek advice and use religious leaders to attack and campaign against their opponents, whereas politics and religion are supposed to be independent institutions sometimes. The negative use of religion may lead to injustice and corruption against the masses. The researchers made use of secondary sources of data collection in their methodology which comprises of books, Journals, magazines, as well as encyclopaedia and other relevant materials to the study. The findings of this research show that the manipulation of religion by political Gladiators in Nigerian politics cannot be overemphasized because religion or organization has been manipulated and still manipulating political decisions of successive governments since independence to date. Religion has been a dominant factor in Nigerian politics. Therefore, every religious group should help to encourage religious freedom whereby everybody will be free to seek the truth without any coercion or inhibition. Religious leaders of the two major religions in Nigeria must seek ways and means to form forums for mutual understanding collaboration and dialogue independent of government interference and political manipulation. If all these are observed, the manipulation of religion by political gladiators and orientation will cease, politicians will elect candidates sbased on capability and religion will cease to be an agent of disunity and backwardness.`

Keywords: Manipulation, Religion, Political Gladiators and Orientation

Introduction

Religion has been a dominant or indispensable tool in Nigeria, especially in our present society. In whichever way one sees religion the fact cannot be denied of its interaction with politics in Nigeria. It has become an important tool in the political sphere in Nigeria. The manipulation of Religion by Political Gladiators is not only limited to politicians but its power influences virtually all aspects of life. Power affects, social relations, educational advancement and the psyche of society. Many scholars have postulated several definitions of religion; however, there is no concise meaning for it because there are problems in defining religion. Bolaji E. Edowu “argues that religion is a difficult topic to handle, whether we are considering its connotations, its origins or its definition.”¹

Collins Ugwu, defines “religion as faith and practices involving the relationship between Mankind and what is regarded as scared in a more comprehensive manner.”² Merriam Webster, sees religion as “the outward existence of God to whom obedience, service and honour are due, the feeling or expression of human love, fear or awe of some superhuman and overruling power, whether by observance of rites and ceremonies or by the conduct of life”.³ Similarly, Watkins Angels opines that “political Gladiators are positioning themselves along the ideological continuum. Politics is any activity that shapes, affects, directs or involves the political Sphere, Political participation ranges from campaigns to attending a rally to committing an act of voting and sending someone to be a representative, there is political manipulation of religion since it is the best card politicians can use to get the support of the masses.”⁴

David Kajom noted that “the Elite and the politicians often manipulate or influence government policies for their selfish purposes. One specific meaning of religious manipulations refers to psychological manipulations and harm inflicted on a person by using the teachings of their religion. This is perpetrated by members of the same or similar faith and includes the use of a position of authority within the religion. Manipulation is the exercise of harmful influence over others. People who manipulate others attack their mental and emotional sides to get what they want. The person doing the manipulating is called the manipulator; he seeks to create an unbalance of power”.⁵ Manipulation means to control or play upon by artful, unfair, or insidious means, especially the ones over advantage being used and manipulated by the known men around him. The word Orientation simply means the act of directing someone towards particular things or changing a person's basic beliefs or feelings about a particular subject on religion or politics.

The Manipulation of Religion by Political Gladiators and Orientation

Manipulation is the usage of psychological influence over a person or situation to gain a positive outcome. According to Yusuf Bala Usman, “defines manipulation as “essentially controlling the action of a person or group without that person or group knowing the goals, purpose and method of that control and without even being aware that a form of control is being exercised on them at all”.⁶ By this scholarly definition, Usman is of the view that people can be indoctrinated and manipulated to achieve a particular target or objective. The manipulation of religion in Nigeria is deeply rooted in the poor socio-economic conditions of Nigerians that are rapidly deteriorating and only a microscopic few of the upper class enjoy the high standards of living while the lower class continue to drown in abject poverty and psychological depression. This is done under the disguise of religion to bring division among the people of Nigeria. An example of such manipulation is explained by Alamu in Ladan-Barki where he explained how the organization recruits its members who are mostly the poor then brainwashes them and offers them huge amounts of money ranging from 100,000 to 200,000,000 Naira to either become foot soldiers or suicide bombers.”⁷

The cacophony of voices raised on mundane issues distracts in the main. The manipulation of masses of the people by the elites is not just starting. It has always been the case since the advent of the colonialists till date. The purpose is to grab political power for relevance and the attendant privileges. Beyond promises, freely given during campaigns, very few of the members of this exclusive class spare any serious thoughts for the general well-being of the masses. Any little opportunity, offered by socio-economic crises, is appropriated to wreak maximum havoc

The downtrodden are clothed with religious identities which suit the political whims of the manipulators. The sentiment of religion is employed as a weapon of mass mobilization to confuse the easily impressionable. The real issues are relegated or taken down, completely from political discourse and replaced with manipulative and emotive outbursts to achieve desired goal.

There are three dominant religions in Nigeria, namely African Traditional Religions Christianity and Islam. All these religions and their ideologies allow for interaction between religion and politics. The Traditional religions of a society are a systematic reflection of their socio-cultural orientation, history and legacies on elemental forces, which in turn produces a belief in a supreme cosmic power belonging to all things in their social psyche. This traditional practice of the people had a strong linkage to belief in theocracy. After conducting elections in Nigeria, duringswearing-inceremonies, the oath of office is administered to whoever is elected or declared the winner. The main thrust of the oath is the promise to act faithfully following the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. In doing this, the help of God is solicited. Religious leaders are not given specific roles to play. When the oath is being administered, the mention of God’s name coupled with the holding of scripture or any religious books or objects is enough to establish the inn vocation of the divine.

Ishaq L. Akintola states that “Islam as a way of life dictates and governs the totality of the life of Muslims from cradle to grave. Consequently, this political interest, economic considerations, social values and interactions are often given Islamic interpretation based on the Holy Qur'an. Prophetic practices and other sources of law are

recognized in Islam. These virtues are expected to permeate the socio-political structure of any Islamic State. Prophet Mohammad SAW was the spiritual as well as the political leader of his people during his lifetime. After his death, the Caliphs emerged and still held to the same principles, regardless of the nature of the society. Islam encourages Muslims to hold on to its principles by allowing the Holy Quran and the Sunnah to be their guide. Islam allows for a spiritual relationship between religion and politics.”⁸ Similarly, Amr Abdalla writing from an Islamic perspective suggests that “Islam is a way of life, which dictates, directs, and orientates the political ideology and practice in any Islamic society. He points out that the ideals of Islam are good and are meant to guide political conduct, however, the practices of such ideas are usually influenced by the socio-cultural institutions in the society, including politics.”⁹

Matthew Kukah reveals that for many Muslims, Islam is a total way of life. It is not correct according to this viewpoint to speak of religion and political affiliation but instead of religio-practices. Islam is believed to be relevant and integral to politics, law, education, social life and economy. These are not viewed as secular institutions or areas of life but as aspects of support. In addition, it was observed that no one can aspire to, or hold political office in a country like Nigeria without manipulation of religion or pretending to be religious.¹⁰ Leo Igwe in his view, explain that “Religion goes hand-in-hand with politics, and it will be difficult to hold a public office without holding ontoreligious affiliation and orientation. Politicians make use of the power entrenched in religions, not only to achieve their aims but also to subjugate their opponents and to legitimize their religion. For this reason, the dominant religion groups, Islam, and Christianity have been locked in a fierce battle for the political contract of the country.”¹¹

Sanusi N. Wali, asserts that “religion is the people's way of life including both their tradition and social interaction. It is man's integral attitude to life. From the dawn of his creation, man has never been divorced from religion. Whatever kind it may be, is important to note, that religion possesses great functional value and as a dimension of human life, is believed to have been present since time immemorial. Hence, it is glaring that people attached a strong significance to religion. It controls man in its entirety; it shows that men cannot do without religion regardless of what he/she believes in.”¹² In addition, religion stimulates man to control his environment by struggling for power, to achieve his objectives. Religion empowers man to pursue political power and other forms of power that can allow him to have firm control of his environment. The access to the powers that religion guise to man makes religion inseparable from political orientation.

Akpenpuun Dzugba asserts that “political gladiator and orientation do not have a common definition rather it is the activity in which people make, preserve and amend the general rules under which they live. As such, it is an essentially social activity, metrically linked on the one hand to the existence of diversity and conflict and on the other hand, to a willingness to cooperate and act collectively. Political gladiators require a constitution and political parties, it involves ideology, it includes criticism (opinion) it requires the public and the state which is made up of individuals, and it is about the acquisition of power and the use of such power”.¹³ Nkem Onyekpe define it as a “struggle for power which itself is the authority to determine or formulate and execute decisions and policies which must be accepted by the society, it is the struggle for power of governance especially executive authority.”¹⁴

From the aforementioned political gladiators is everyone's affair. We make use of politics in our homes, offices, schools, organizations, churches, mosques etc. it is about control supremacy and authority. Hence, there is an element of power in religion and politics. In a joint pastoral letter, the Catholic Bishops Conference of Nigeria emphasizes the Civic and political responsibilities of all Christians stating that: “It is the noble right and serious duty of every responsible citizen to do what he can towards the establishment, maintenance and successful operation of a good government.” Furthermore Peter Schinneller opines that “the prospective voter should be convinced of the importance of his vote. Neglecting is the denial of potential support for social justice and progress, voting conscientiously and purposefully is the citizen's most available and direct way of contributing to the election of most suitable leaders and support of beneficial policies. It is also in this sense that selling one's vote or cashing it for short-sighted gain is offensive before God and man.”¹⁵

Femi Falana, a Senior Advocate of Nigeria (SAN) opines that the manipulation of religion by political gladiators and orientation is carried out by some powerful individuals who hide under the guise of religion to pursue selfish interests and the greediness of some religious leaders who patronize corrupt rulers remains part of the negative effects of religion on politics. Greed has entered into the religious terrain to the extent that some religious leaders now patronize corrupt rulers to meet their lust for money and other material gains. Efforts by Nigerian politicians to gain ascendancy and power have led to a situation in which politics have swept away sacred precepts of people with bitterness and enmity for the religion of others.¹⁶

Nigeria was a colonial creation over 50 years ago. It is an entity of three major religious groups namely Christian, Islam and African Traditional Religion. Christianity and Islam are the dominant forms of religious practice, while a good proportion of people mix either Christianity or Islam with African religion (ATR). In Nigeria one of the most easily or widely recognized features of individuals, groups, and aside from their ethnicity is religion. Religion features manifestations and permeates actions such as simple receiving of visitors, solemnizing of relations, preparation for farming or other ceremonials or productive enterprises in rural areas. While in urban centres, political gatherings and project commissioning, occasions such as official meetings, policy deliberations, school activities, ceremonies, sports, businesses whatever form of gathering formal or informal are always committed to the lord's guidance and protection in its opening or closing sessions.

The acceptability and vitality of religious orientation, as an integral aspect of the Nigerian people and its protection has been recognized in the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria thus: that "every person shall be entitled to freedom of thought, conscience and religion, including the freedom to change his religion or belief, and freedom (either alone or in community with others, and in public or in private) to manifest and propagate his religion or belief in worship, teaching, preaching and observance.

Theoretical Framework: Structural Theory

This theory is also called functionalism, sees society as structure with interrelated parts designed to meet the biological and social needs of the individuals in the society. Titchener, who invented the term structuralism. Though Titchener is usually the one credited with the establishment of structuralism and bringing the ideas to America, the ideas started with Wundt <https://www.verywellmind.com>. This theory has two main sub-orientations. The first is the radical structural theory represented by the Marxist dialectical school with exponents like Marx and Engels, V.I. Lenin, etc. The second is the liberal structuralism represented by Ross Marc, and the famous work of Johan Galtung on structural violence. It is also sometimes similar to transformative theory, which addresses the reactions of individuals, groups, religion, politics, cultures, institutions and societies to change. It further sees incompatible interests based on competition for resources, which in most cases are assumed to be scarce, as being responsible for social conflicts.¹⁷

The main argument of the structural conflict theory is that conflict is built into the particular ways societies are structured and organised. The theory looks at social problems like, religion, political and economic exclusion, injustice, disease, exploitation, inequity etc., as sources of conflict. Structuralisms maintain that conflicts occur because of the exploitative and unjust nature of human societies, domination of one class by another, etc. This case is made by radicals like Friedrich Engels, Karl Marx, Joseph Lenin and Mao Tse Tung, who blame capitalism for being an exploitative system based on its relations of production and the division of society into the proletariat and the bourgeoisie. The exploitation of the proletariat and lower classes under capitalism creates conflict. Thus, capitalist societies are accused of being exploitative, and such exploitation is a cause of conflict. Capitalist conflict, to Marxists, will be resolved through a revolution where the bourgeoisie will be overthrown in a socialist revolution led by workers, bringing about the establishment of a socialist order led by the working people. Furthermore, there will be "capitalist internationalism", a situation where workers all over the world unite, and will not be limited by state boundaries, since the state itself is an artificial creation of the bourgeoisie to dominate others.

Spinner-Hale's emphasis on the theological foundations of the liberal framework of religion obscures the importance of the changing historical and political circumstances in which discussions about religion, secularism, toleration and non-establishment take place. For not only theology, but also shifting political affiliation, interests and conflicts play a role in religion's historical narrative. In addition Rose Marc looks at the Spinner-Hale's reasoning also ignores that early modern discussions on toleration were strongly influenced by the political contexts in which they took place. Ideas about religious difference most certainly play a role in these discussions. However, it is important to examine the way in which these differences were 'put to use' in serving different political interests. Both the work of John Locke and the discussions and policies of toleration in seventeenth-century England problematize the idea that early liberalism was internally tolerant and that Protestant theological principles were leading in the extension of tolerance.¹⁸

The long eighteenth century was a period in which 'religion was remade and given new forms and meanings'. A focus on the persistent nature of Religious concepts, however, suggests *continuity* and overlooks the transformations that took place. One of these transformations was the way in which religion came to be seen as a marker of European, sometimes national, culture or civilization. The period's views on Judaism, Islam and Others show how 'religion' became entangled in the creation of ethno cultural hierarchies. This becomes visible in the work of Montesquieu, who connects religion and culture, both being the outcome of the climate in which people live, and in the work of those Enlightenment scholars who project problematic features such as fanaticism and despotism

The Marxist tradition has been extended by neo-Marxists, mostly of the Underdevelopment and Dependency School, most of them from the developing countries. Some of the best-known theorists are Andre Gunder Frank, Walter Rodney, Samir Amin, as well as Emanuel Wallerstein who expounded the "world system theory". This group of scholars seeks to explain the reasons for development and underdevelopment, and why the third world is not developing. They situate their analysis within the world capitalist system, and accuse the system of being structurally exploitative, retarding development for the Third World. Walter Rodney in his book *How Europe Underdeveloped Africa* differentiates between Underdevelopment and non-development. He says non-development takes place when a country is not developing due to any external forces accounting for its stagnation. However, underdevelopment occurs when another external factor, a nation, is responsible for the situation, such as Europe destroying the basis and foundations for African development through its various historical relations with the continent.

Applicability of Structural Theory to the Study

The emphasis of structural theory is thus on how the competing interests of groups tie conflict directly into the social, economic, and political affiliation and orientation of society as well as the nature and strength of social networks within and between community groups. Ross and Johan noted for instance that, in situations where economic, religion orientation and political discrimination and weak kinship ties are the defining characteristics of a society, the chances that negative forms of conflict will result are higher than in situations where the conditions are the exact opposite. In other words, when social, religion, political, economic and cultural processes are monopolised by a group, it creates the conditions that make people to adopt adversarial approaches to conflict.¹⁹

According to Miloon Kothari a former Director of the United Nation's University's programme on Peace and Global Transformation, that influence of religion on political affiliation and orientation is a major cause of conflict between individuals and groups within political systems and between nations. As he puts it, "the control and use of (natural) resources lies at the heart of the deepening crisis in the world today".²⁰ He describes this crisis as separating the world into axes of material comfort and of deficiency with a concentration of poverty and scarcity and unemployment and deprivation in one large sector of mankind (underdeveloped countries) and of overabundance and overproduction in another much smaller section (developed countries).²¹

Grace Scarborough asserts that in situations where existing structures are tilted in favour of one group while putting the other(s) at a disadvantage as amply illustrated in Kothari's unequal axes above; where cultures are seen as exclusive; where holders of certain powers or privileges are unwilling to acknowledge the rights of others to be different; or where people find it difficult to identify with the political and economic ideas of a political regime, the chances are that conflict will emerge and escalate if nothing is done to correct such anomalies.²² Making the type of orientation that will lead to positive relationships requires a change of tactics, but change is often resisted not because people do not see its positive values, but because they are not so keen to admit their blunders which in fact may be induced from within or by factors outside the immediate control of the religious and political leaders..

Structural theory is remarkably strong on the immediate and underlying factors that lead to conflict. It presents a large number of such factors that make the emergence and escalation of internal conflicts possible. Michael Brown is of the view that while “economic and social factors are more common, political and institutional factors (the structure of the state, discriminatory on religion, political institutions, intergroup politics and elite cohesion or fragmentation); security factors (national security dilemma, regional military environment, refugee regimes, cross-border criminality, and civil- military relations); as well as ethnic factors: (demography and physical geography), are equally as critical.”²³ There may be a need to look at the position of structural conflict theory again because of its narrow focus on material interests. It is possible that in trying to explain the severity of internal conflicts, material interests may also be the result of certain psychological needs, which would better explain the intensity, duration and outcome of internal conflicts.

Some Clear Socio-Economic and Political Issues Involving Manipulation of Religion in Nigeria

As stated in section 10 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, the government of the federation shall not adopt any religion as a state Religion. Therefore, in policy formulation, government, and other governmental activities, religion should not be an issue. By implications, every citizen has a right to freedom of thought, conscience, and religion. Samuel Kalu also observed the following reasons for the manipulation of religion by political gladiators and orientation:

- a. Seeking popularity: religions and political leaders in Nigeria are known to manipulate their fellows to display their popularity and create recognition for themselves. We do believe the real religious teachings are humility; piety and forgiveness are the watchwords. This is as presented by Samuel Kalu ,who illustrates Islam and asserts: "Many other passages could be collated to underscore the emphasis on humility in the exercise of power, charity in social relations and sensitivity to the need of the poor and the weak communalism which is a core value in traditional ethics is reinforced by the second ethical core in Islam, namely the mandates of brotherly spirit." Relatively, in the Christian religion Samuel Kalu also says that certain values persist: Jesus emphasizes a certain perception that the use of power should be characterised by humility and servant hood. The greatest should be the servant of all. Hubris has no place he criticized the Roman imperial authority, the rulers of the temple, and the educated elite who used casuistry and legalism as subterfuges to avoid charity and sensitivity to the needs of the poor he thought and demonstrated that God cared for the material and physical wellbeing of all men, for justice and their spiritual growth.
- b. Illiteracy: In Nigeria, there is a low level of literacy and a prevalence of social problems. These were manipulated by elites and other opportunists in the name of religion to cause discord and damage.
- c. Injustice: Nigeria is a country where justice can be sold and bought and it is a nation where every necessary means can be employed to gain social political or economic favours. Religious influence becomes a soft tool in seeking justice. Several studies have grounded the phenomena of Boko-Haram under seeking justice for the life of the slated leader.²⁴

Yusuf Bala also observed the following:

- i. Corrupt, political and economic gains: In Nigeria, it is proven that religion is no longer merely about the control of the theological space, but also an arena of accumulation. This underscores the increasing influences of religion in the political economy of the state and the tendencies for geo-ethnic-religion posture to defend the 'nation's cake.' These observations particularly played out in the build-up to the 2011 general elections in the country and the pattern of voting that ushered in 5th May 2011, democratic dispensation. The series of events such as the 1st of October 2011 bombings in Abuja, police headquarters and UN bombings, the insurgency of Boko Haram, secessions threats that accompanied the dawn of the new government in Nigeria are blamed by the government and its agencies on religious bigotry.²⁵
- ii. Acting out oppression: Religion is manipulated to act out the feeling of being oppressed by the segment of religion or Sect in Nigeria. Poverty, poor or lack of education, unemployment and other social malaises pinches individual groups severely. This invariably leads to criminality; kidnapping and terror (Boko-Haram) and where bureaucrats and technocrats jettison ethics and principles in the course of discharging official responsibilities, religion's fervent are referred to and exploited, fanatically. This is in tendon with Kalu's assertion that, sometimes religious fervency is portrayed as a field for the oppressed-political, social or economic deprivation.²⁶
- iii. During the military regime in Nigeria, there was a time when the Head of State chose a Muslim as his deputy. After that, the scenario changed, as we can see Both Abacha and Abubakar picked Diya and Akhigbe (Christians) as their Deputies respectively. During the civilian regime, the Obasanjo/Atiku regime was Christian/Muslim. Yar'dua/Jonathan was Muslim/Christian, Jonathan/Sambo was Christian/Muslim and the last regime of Buhari/Osibanjo was Muslim/Christian. In subsequent political dispensations, religion has been a sensitive factor in choosing principal officers at the two levels of the National Assemble. These instances show that political parties and administrations recognized religion as a factor in governance. It is also an issue that voting and campaigning, in some cases, are based on religious sentiment.²⁷

Other Causes of Religious Manipulation in Nigerian Society

1. Poverty: this occurs as a result of abject poverty. When an individual is poor he/she can easily be manipulated. For example, one can be psyched to kill somebody who is not his religious member and he will have the reward here on earth and the last day; looking at his critical condition he can easily succumb to get a daily bread.

2. Ignorance of adherents about other faiths: it refers to the inability to know other people's beliefs then you go about believing and acting towards a feeble statement towards their faith and doctrine.

3. The media's sensational reports of religious conflicts: this occurs under the guidance of some reporters by the state holders. Regarding this, the reporters will be manipulated to make any report in favour of the person in the seat so as not to lose his/her job.

4. Religious fanaticism: this involves excessive intolerance of opposing other religions. In this, the spirit of religiosity controls the life of victims. It binds their eyes to any other truths or causes, natural, logical and other views. This as a cause of religious manipulation usually insists that if others do not follow their ways, they will be damned

Muhammad Yusuf in this case, religion could be used to either canvass support for a candidate or dissuade the electorate from voting for him or her. After conducting elections in Nigeria, during swearing-inceremonies, the oath of office is administered to whoever is elected or declared as such. The main thrust of the oath is the promise to act faithfully and following the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. In doing this, the help of God is solicited. Though religious leaders are not given specific roles to play when oath of office is administered, the mention of God's name, coupled with the holding of scripture or any religious object is enough to establish the invocation of the divine. It must be understood as a chance of occurrence that states like Sokoto,

Zamfara, Kebbi and Kano, among others, has never produced Christian governors. And States like Plateau State and Benue State have never produced Muslim governors. In 2010, the issue of swearing in the then-deputy governor of Kaduna State, who is a Christian, as the governor of the state generated a crisis in the state when the then-governor of the state Namadi Sambo was adopted by President Goodluck Jonathan as the vice president of Nigeria.²⁸ He further said that the questions that come to mind at this juncture are; what relevance is religion in the choice of candidates? Does religion determine the level of competence and performance of a leader? Nigerians do influence religion for their selfish ends in ensuring electoral victory. Ironically, this does not guarantee good governance.²⁹

The recent happenings in the country, especially the Boko Haram attack, herdsmen crisis and recurring ethno-religious violence in Northern Nigeria, among others, suggest the strong influence of religion in Nigeria. Religion provides mankind with moral values by which to live. Samuel Nnadi reveals that "religion is often used to subvert political needs and aspirations of the ruling class. Religion is positively used to promote the political life of any society. Every religion, whether Christianity, Islam African Traditional Religion, etc, has moral values which regulate and harmonize human life. In Exodus 20 of the Christian Bible, there is an outline of the Ten Commandments which guide the behaviours of Christians in society. In the same way, Islam and African Traditional Religion (ATR) have rules, which their adherents must obey".³⁰ This shows that no religion condones immorality. Highlighting the function of religion as a provider of moral values, John Mbiti in Patrick Nmah, says, "It is religion which tells what is right, and what is wrong. Religion enriches people's morale for the welfare of the individual and society at large", adherence to religious ethical values are imperative for all religious practitioners.³¹

Interestingly, Nigerians are one of the most religious people in the world theoretically, as posted by Joseph Omeregebe, there is a need to live a moral life because it is commanded by God. Failure to do this will be counterproductive in the matter of national development. Religion, being an agent of social control, helps to keep with the norm, of the society, which is the real basis of politics. Furthermore, religion breeds an ideal heart in man to be conscious of the need to have a clean heart. By this, he will grow to have a philanthropic or patriotic thought before venturing to lead or represent his people in the government of the state. In other words, religion will prepare the mind of man to be a good politician who will constantly fall back upon his religion to guide him. The teaching or threats of religion is expected to guide him to be able to lead his people right as a politician with fear of God in him.³² He will never consider himself first; rather he knows that he is the servant of the electorates. Without mincing words, a free election will produce legitimate leaders who will govern with the fear of God; and obedient followers. Achieving this will solve problems, such as religious influence, political orientation, sentiment or selfishness and insecurity, maladministration.

True democracy is dependent upon free, fair and credible election, a situation whereby the electorates are free to elect their leaders. The elected leaders will in turn to sustain the rule of law, which is the benchmark of any true democracy in a civilized society. Many of them are simply after what they stand to gain. Moreover, where people vote on religious sentiment, mediocre leaders are the most likely to emerge and, when this happens, growth and development will be retarded. The negative impact of religion in Nigerian politics is increasingly manifested in the nation. Every political process in Nigeria has a religious undertone. The civil service, appointment to important positions in the government, and the entire body politics of the nation are seriously influenced by religious prejudice. Many Nigerians are now refusing to post or transfer to some parts of the country because of the manner religion is being handled in Nigeria. This ugly situation continues hampering national development in the country.

The Positive Effects of the Manipulation of Religion by Political Gladiators

The positive effect of the manipulation of religion by political gladiators is the adherence to the oath of office. In this case, political leaders, having invoked God when the oath is being administered, will rule with the fear of God. We must be cognizant of the fact that every content of the oath is a guarantee for good governance if imbibed. In practice, the positive implication is hypothetical as religious moral values have not impacted governance in Nigeria since independence. Whereas, none of the rulers, past or present, has claimed or claim not to be religious. What has been experienced is the manipulation of religion for selfish gains or interests.

Negative Effects Onmanipulation of Religion by Political Gladiators

The manipulation of religion by politicians has, at various times, threatened the corporate existence of Nigeria. For example, the issue of serious arguments brought the Constituent Assseriousto an abrupt end in 1978, given the walkout that was staged by some Muslim members and some non-Muslims. This wouldn't have arisen if the secular/pluralistic nature of the country had been respected. Religious crises have further worsened inter- Ethnic animosity. The Kaduna and Joss ethno-religious crises displaced many people who had settled in the northern part of the Country for many years as it became necessary for them to relocate to a safer environment.

John Okafor explains that the effect on influence of religious affiliation and orientation on politics has brought about people voting according to their faith regardless, of the capacity of the candidate to lead the state or the Country. This was evident in the southeast, for example a Catholic Priest in Anambra state openly enjoined the members to vote for Peter Obi (former Governor) because of his religious inclination. Also, the former People's Democratic Party (PDP) Senator for Jigawa North-west senatorial district Danladi Sankara decried an alleged religious undertone in the 2011 presidential election Sankara who was also the Jonathan/Sambo returning agent for Jigawa State in the election, indicated that there was connivance among the opposition parties in Jigawa whereby they indoctrinated the people to vote for Congress for Progressive Change (CPC) Candidate.³³

Religion has influenced how the state power is captured, this can be seen in the political statements of religious institutions, their choice of candidates and the inclination of candidates to turn to their religious communities for support whether the candidates are capable or credible to lead or not. Religion is a way of life for many people in Nigeria. It has a direct impact on their social and political decisions. The issue here is that a religious community could insist on voting one of its members into office even if the candidate is generally considered to be a misfit. The danger is this inter-religious conflict could be ignited if one religious group rejects the candidates of another, or if a politician mobilises his religious community against his opponents in another religion. There is the threat that citizens could be excluded from the political process. If a religious community, underepresented, is allowed to dominate the political space, it could prevent minorities from having a say and being represented in government.

Recommendations

Based on the above discussion the following recommendations were made:

1. Political leaders of the three major religions in Nigeria must seek ways and means to form forums for mutual understanding, collaboration and dialogue independent of government interference and political orientations
2. The constitution should be politically adhered to while the influence of religion on politics should be avoided by all stakeholders. Also, those who are found guilty of using religion for their political interest in society must be made to face the wrath of the law according to the severity of their offences.
3. The judiciary should be an independent body and every necessary incentive or support should be given to it to enable play its role fearlessly. The issue of the immunity clause should not arise because the rule of law stipulates equality.
4. Politicians should stop influencing religion on political matters so that credible and capable candidates would be elected. If all these were observed, religion would cease to be an agent of disunity and backwardness.

Conclusion

This research has concluded that the influence of religion on political affiliation and orientation particularly in Nigeria which started after independence should stop. The influence of religion on politics has negative effects which always lead to crisis and underdevelopment, without mincing words, the role religion could play in Nigerian politics should be limited by the individual's orientation due to the nature of the society. Despite these limitations, religion continues to influence the political decisions of the successive governments of this country.

Endnotes

- ¹Bolaji E. Edowu, *African Tradition Religion. A definition* (London: SCM Print 1973), 11.
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